

WebODM free software as a tool for digital aerial photogrammetric processing: employability in scientific productions

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Abstract

With the advancement of technologies applied to Global Navigation Satellite Systems and the popularization of Remotely Piloted Aircraft, aerial photogrammetry has experienced significant advances, especially in geographic and environmental research. Drones equipped with high-resolution sensors have revolutionized data collection, essential for topographic mapping and vegetation analysis. However, many technologies for digital processing and spatial analysis of original images are proprietary and expensive, making access difficult for institutions and researchers, especially in Brazil. This scenario makes free and open-source software, such as WebODM, an important alternative to democratize access to high-quality tools. In view of this, this article analyzes the applicability of WebODM in academic works, through bibliometric analysis in scientific repositories. The search included variations in the software nomenclature and the data were analyzed quantitatively. The Elsevier and Scopus databases led with 59 and 39 publications, respectively, while the national Scielo Brasil database had only one article hosted. There has been a gradual increase in the number of publications involving WebODM since 2016, with a peak of 38 papers in 2023. In comparison, the term "Agisoft Metashape", a proprietary solution for digital aerial photogrammetric processing, returned 1,595 publications in the same search portals. As an initial contribution to the understanding of the state of the art, it was observed that the thematic axes involving remote sensing, photogrammetry, precision agriculture and agricultural management were those that concentrated the largest number of scientific productions on WebODM in the investigated period, exceeding 30 papers. It is concluded that WebODM has stood out as a relevant tool in scientific research, especially for the processing of images derived from drones. Future studies should qualitatively evaluate the results obtained with the use of WebODM in comparison with proprietary software.

1. Introduction

With the improvement of technologies applied to Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) and the advent of Remotely Piloted Aircraft (RPA), aerial photogrammetry has experienced significant advances in recent years, especially in the context applied to geographic research and environmental issues (Paz & Sampaio, 2019).

The use of RPAs, popularly referred to as drones, equipped with high spatial resolution sensors has revolutionized the collection of primary data in scientific research. These devices allow the capture of detailed images, essential for topographic mapping, vegetation analysis, and identification of specific targets on the surface.

However, most of the advanced technologies for digital processing and spatial analysis of images derived from RPAs are proprietary, with acquisition or licensing plans that can be expensive for many institutions or individual researchers, especially in Brazil. As popular examples, one can highlight the proprietary solutions Agisoft Metashape and Pix4D Mapper, the costs of which exceed three and a half thousand dollars, as highlighted on the vendors' websites.

This financial barrier often makes it impossible to conduct in-depth studies in the fields of geosciences, especially in contexts where resources are limited and there is a need to survey and process topographic data in the field. In this scenario, free and open source software (FOSS), such as Open Drone Map (ODM), is important for democratizing access to advanced tools capable of meeting the quality requirements in cartography for analysis and mapping, without compromising the accuracy and reliability of the results.

Its user-friendly interface, called WebODM, offers a free and robust solution for digital processing of drone images, based on the ability to simulate the "structure from motion" of sensor systems (Carrivick *et al.*, 2016). It allows the creation of orthophotomosaics, Digital Terrain Models (DTM), Digital Surface Models (DSM), three-dimensional point clouds, among other derived products, which are essential for environmental analysis (Open Drone Map Authors, 2020).

Compared to proprietary solutions, WebODM stands out for its accessibility and flexibility, although it is necessary to evaluate its effectiveness and compare it with commercial alternatives (Machado, 2024), especially in scientific applications.

In this context, the present study aims to analyze the employability of the free software for digital aerial photogrammetric processing WebODM in academic works,

based on bibliometric analysis of data from the main repositories of scientific journals.

2. Methodology

To achieve the results, the research adopted a bibliometric analysis method to investigate how global scientific production has portrayed the use of WebODM in articles, reviews, book chapters, and other publications. The hosting portals of the main scientific journals were consulted, such as Scopus, Science Direct (Elsevier), Scielo Brasil, Web of Science (WOS), as well as the publishers Taylor & Francis Online and Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI). Access was free of charge through the list of databases and journal collections made available by CAPES/MEC.

Figure 1 illustrates the steps taken for the bibliometric analysis. The search exercise, in order to cover the largest possible number of works, did not apply any temporal filter to the searched terms. In total, the following search keys were searched: “Web ODM” OR “WebODM” OR “OpenDroneMap” OR “Open DroneMap” OR “Open Drone Map”. These keys were selected to cover all nomenclature variations associated with publications involving the use of the WebODM software.

Figure 1. Methodological flowchart of the research.

The data collected from the bibliometric search were downloaded into Excel spreadsheets for quantitative analysis and graphing. The methods employed here, therefore, focus on a quantitative-descriptive review of an exploratory nature, including counting publications by year, distribution by database, and categorization by thematic axes. The objective was to identify the frequency and evolution of the use of WebODM software in the scientific productions reviewed, without, however, evaluating in depth the quality and/or impact of the works analyzed.

From the data set, the publications were classified into five thematic axes, based on the analysis of titles and keywords. These categories reflect the main research fields in which WebODM has been applied by the academic community. In addition, the potentialities and limitations of WebODM were discussed, especially in comparison with Agisoft Metashape, one of the main competing commercial tools.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Overview of Open Drone Map, potential and limitations

Open Drone Map is understood as an ecosystem of open-source tools for mapping and three-dimensional surface modeling, which includes solutions such as WebODM, NodeODM and PyODM. As open source software, it allows customization according to the user's needs, with a strong community of

developers contributing to continuous improvements. It has distributed processing capacity, allowing the use of multiple machines to handle large volumes of data, in addition to supporting multiple input and output formats, including GeoTIFF, OBJ, PLY and LAS, facilitating integration with other GIS and CAD software.

It has clear workflows, which begin with the upload of images captured by RPAs with a minimum frontal and lateral overlap of 65%, depending on the characteristics of the study area. It has a user-friendly and intuitive interface, which optimizes the management and visualization of projects and products, as highlighted in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2. Overview of the WebODM interface, highlighting orthophotomosaic (a), Digital Surface Model (b) and plant health indicator (c) in an example region in Southeast Brazil.

Compared to Agisoft Metashape, it stands out for its accessibility, since it can be installed and used without the need for a license or paid subscription, and for its scalability, given its distributed processing capacity, which allows it to handle larger and more complex projects without the need for a high-performance machine.

Recent scientific literature has highlighted the relevance of WebODM for digital aerial photogrammetric processing and its

role as an integral part of free and robust GIS solutions for application in various research themes. Authors such as Vacca (2020) and Mattivi *et al.* (2021) evaluated, respectively, the geometric and positional quality of point clouds of the same area processed by both ODM and Metashape, and the effectiveness of ODM, in integration with QGIS, SAGA and OpenCV algorithms, for supervised classification and mapping of weeds in agricultural areas in Italy. In both cases, WebODM achieved the objectives proposed by the authors, offering products with the expected technical rigor.

In a review article on the set of open-source tools available for capturing and processing aerial photogrammetric data in scientific applications, Pereyra-Irujo *et al.* (2023) also highlighted the high quality of the results from WebODM compared to commonly used proprietary solutions. On the other hand, in scenarios with inconsistent lighting conditions or inadequate overlap rates between images, the authors point out that WebODM may perform worse than the most popular proprietary software, due to limitations in the algorithms or their optimization.

Nevertheless, it is observed that there is a trend in the academic community towards highlighting WebODM as the main and most promising free software for aerial photogrammetric processing available to date, whose evolution in relevance in the scientific community will be presented by the results of the bibliometric analysis below.

3.2. Bibliometric analysis

The bibliometric analysis carried out revealed a general overview of the use of WebODM in scientific research, with 144 works identified that adhered to the search terms used.

The results indicated that publications in the Elsevier database have the largest number of academic works, totaling 59, followed by Scopus, with 39. Web of Science presented 25 publications. In contrast, Scielo Brasil showed only one publication. The publishers consulted registered 12 and nine publications (Taylor & Francis Online and Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute, respectively). The oldest publications dated back to 2016.

The quantitative distribution illustrated in Figure 3 below shows that international databases, such as Scopus, Elsevier and Web of Science, concentrate the majority of publications related to the use of WebODM in the academic environment. In addition, they tend to have a larger collection and demand for publication. On the other hand, regional databases, such as Scielo Brasil, may suggest lower adoption of the software by the national scientific community and/or the predominance of studies produced in English.

It is also worth noting that the lower number of publications observed in the Brazilian context may be related to the high costs of acquiring and maintaining RPAs by federal universities, which consequently impacts the adoption of processing solutions, whether proprietary or open-source.

Figure 3. Number of publications by source consulted.

The temporal analysis of publications related to the use of WebODM revealed reasonable and relatively continuous growth over the years. In the first two years after the launch of the tool, in 2014, there were no publications recorded. In 2016, the number of works was only two, while in the following years there was a gradual increase, with 15 scientific productions recorded in 2019.

As illustrated in Figure 4, from 2021 onwards, there was a continuous increase in the number of publications involving WebODM, with 18 works recorded in 2021, 27 in 2022 and a peak of 38 in 2023. In 2024, up to the time of the bibliometric review, there were 24 productions, totaling 145 publications. The continuous increase in the use of WebODM may be associated with the maturation of open source photogrammetry tools and the growing adoption of RPAs in scientific projects (McDonald, 2019). Furthermore, it is possibly linked to the interest of the academic community in accessible alternatives to proprietary solutions and, mainly, to the greater demand for mapping and monitoring activities in environmental and agricultural areas.

Figura 4. Number of publications per year.

To better understand the context in which WebODM is inserted in scientific research, the 144 publications identified were categorized into five main thematic axes, namely: (1) Remote Sensing and Photogrammetry; (2) Precision Agriculture and Agricultural Management; (3) Infrastructure and Urban Mapping; (4) Environmental Applications; (5) Development of Open-Source Software and Tools. The quantitative distribution of publications in each axis is illustrated in Figure 5 below.

Containing 41 publications, approximately 28% of the total, the thematic axis with the greatest scientific application of WebODM was Remote Sensing and Photogrammetry. In common, the works highlight the generation of point clouds,

orthophotomosaics, and Digital Terrain Models (DTM) and Surface Models (DSM) to create three-dimensional representations of objects, terrains, and buildings (Vacca, 2019; Gbagir *et al.*, 2023). They demonstrate that the use of WebODM for purposes related to the primary survey of topographic data finds support in the academic environment.

Figure 5. Number of publications by major themes.

The second largest group of publications (2) addresses the use of WebODM in the agricultural field, with applications that include crop monitoring (Széles *et al.*, 2024) and biomass estimates (Walter *et al.*, 2018), based on the adoption of RPAs equipped with optical and multispectral sensors. These publications are mostly concentrated in the Web of Science, which indicates the profile of the research lines whose articles were hosted by the portal. It also reveals the growing use of photogrammetry with RPA in the context of agriculture, to monitor crop health and better understand the dynamics of the territory in an agricultural environment.

In the thematic axis focused on research in Infrastructure and Urban Mapping (3), WebODM has been used for land registry purposes and for inspection of critical infrastructures, such as bridges (Morgenthal *et al.*, 2019), solar panels (Oliveira *et al.*, 2023; Meribout *et al.*, 2023) and waste management (Deidun *et al.*, 2018). Publications are concentrated mainly in the Elsevier and Scopus databases, with a focus on the use of 3D models for optimizing building maintenance and monitoring works.

The use of WebODM in Environmental Applications (4), such as monitoring water quality, vegetation, among other variables that depend on the collection and analysis of spatial data (Barnetson *et al.*, 2019), are important research focuses. Publications on this topic are found in smaller numbers, but with increasing relevance in the current scenario, especially in the Elsevier and Taylor & Francis databases.

With 22 publications, the Software Development thematic axis (5) focuses on improvements and integration of WebODM with other open source platforms, reflecting the scientific community's commitment to optimizing the tool's performance (Gbagir *et al.*, 2023). Publications in this field are predominantly found in publishers such as MDPI and Scopus.

In addition, the publications highlight the application of algorithms and computational models, such as the use of artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning and the use of neural networks, integrated with technologies derived from RPAs and remote sensing, as tools to improve data analysis, detect patterns, automate processes, classify objects and make predictions.

The growth illustrated in Figure 5 is in line with the development and popularization of the themes analyzed in the scientific context, reflecting the broad applicability of this open source tool

in several areas, as highlighted by Vacca (2019). The increase in publications on Precision Agriculture, for example, is related to the advancement of the use of remote sensing technologies for crop monitoring. Likewise, interest in Infrastructure and Urban Mapping has been growing as cities face increasing challenges in monitoring and managing resources.

With the evolution of sensors embedded in RPAs, such as hyperspectral and LIDAR, WebODM can expand its use to generate even more complex products, such as the fusion of data from multiple sensors, refinement in the construction of Digital Surface Models, capture of augmented reality, among others. The scientific contribution certainly increases the growth potential of the open-source solution and spreads its importance in the academic environment.

3.3 General contributions to the state of the art

Among the various scientific papers quantified and/or reviewed in the bibliometric analysis effort, the most cited article (53 times) was conducted by Hardin *et al.* (2018), entitled “Small Unmanned Aerial System (sUAS) for Environmental Remote Sensing: Challenges and Opportunities Revisited”. In a review exercise at the time, the study identified six main challenges in the use of small unmanned aerial systems for remote sensing in the environmental area, highlighting obstacles that are currently being continually overcome, such as power limitations, sensor characteristics, payload weight, and technological infrastructure for data analysis.

The authors examined how technological advances would mitigate these problems. With regard to data analysis, for example, the article addresses how processing large volumes of information generated by RPAs, especially aerial images, was, in the past, one of the biggest barriers to the wider adoption of these technologies.

The use of specific software for data processing, such as Pix4D and Drone Deploy, facilitated these tasks. However, the article acknowledges that the emergence of open source tools, such as Open Drone Map, through its WebODM graphical interface, offered viable alternatives to proprietary software. It was described by the authors at the time as a promising initiative that provided an affordable means for processing data derived from RPAs, allowing researchers to perform image post-processing quickly, offering a practical solution to the challenge of handling voluminous data.

The second most cited article in the bibliometric analysis (31), entitled “Drones in Urban Stormwater Management: A Review and Future Perspectives” (McDonald, 2019), addresses the use of RPAs for monitoring and managing urban stormwater. This article highlights the growing relevance of drones in monitoring water flows and quality, emphasizing the potential of emerging technologies, such as Open Drone Map, in the context of urban infrastructure.

The article emphasizes the role of Open Drone Map as an accessible and open-source tool that can provide high-resolution data quickly and at low cost, compared to proprietary solutions. It highlights the ability to produce orthophotomosaics, using techniques that simulate the “structure of movement” and allow the extraction of data from the topographic surface.

The qualitative and quantitative characteristics observed, not only in the bibliometric analysis, but in the bibliographic review of the main authors highlighted, indicate a still timid but growing pattern of adoption of the WebODM software by the scientific community in recent years, in all the thematic axes evaluated.

Although this article did not analyze, in a systematic and individualized manner, the quality of the publications identified, the effort suggests that WebODM has been used as a viable alternative to proprietary solutions, especially in contexts with limited resources. This is particularly relevant in the field of remote sensing, where the high cost of proprietary platforms can be a barrier for small projects or research groups.

A search for the term “Agisoft Metashape” on the same journal hosting portals resulted in 1595 publications, which highlights the predominance of commercial solutions for digital aerial photogrammetric processing in the academic environment. However, the accelerated growth of publications on WebODM reflects a trend towards democratization of technology, expanding access to advanced photogrammetry and remote sensing methodologies.

The data presented suggests that Open Drone Map is gaining ground, as more researchers opt for open source solutions to meet their spatial data analysis needs, reinforcing the impact of free tools on the global scientific scene.

4. Final considerations

The results of the bibliometric analysis highlighted the growing relevance of WebODM in scientific research in recent times. The tool offers a powerful and free solution for processing images derived from RPAs, expanding the possibilities for research and innovation, especially for environmental and agricultural monitoring. WebODM has been consolidating itself as a viable and accessible alternative compared to proprietary software, such as Agisoft Metashape, due to its scalability and ease of integration with other open source software.

Future studies can expand the qualitative evaluation of the publications identified here, exploring in greater depth the effectiveness and results obtained with the use of WebODM in comparison with proprietary software. In addition, the continuous evolution of the tool, as discussed in some of the works cited, suggests an engaged and participatory community, with a view to expanding the free project.

The growth observed in the number of publications on WebODM also reflects an important trend of technological democratization, by allowing researchers with limited resources to have access to advanced tools for digital aerial photogrammetric processing. In this sense, WebODM plays a fundamental role in fostering innovation and the advancement of science on a global scale.

Thus, it is expected that the popularity and impact of WebODM will continue to grow, solidifying its place in the scientific environment as the community of users and researchers grows stronger.

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